

Bhavai: A Seven-Hundred-Year Old Folk Theatre Form in Gujarat

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ABSTRACT

Founded in the fourteenth century, Bhavai reflects the cultural richness of Gujarat. The word “Bhavai” has multiple meanings: ‘Bhav’ (emotions) and vahai (carrier), i.e. “the Carrier of Emotions”; ‘Bhav’ (Universe) and ‘ai’ (Mother), i.e. “the Mother of Universe”, which refers to Goddess Amba. It is a mixture of art, music and dance, which provides entertainment and a tribute to Goddess Amba. This research paper elaborates the origin, the folklore, geographical description and elements of Bhavai. From religious implications to social problems, Bhavai fits into every theme via its distinguished performances, which makes Bhavai as traditional in form but contemporary in objectives. Thus, the present research asserts the elements of Bhavai such as instruments, costumes, makeup, troupes, plot and how the acts of Bhavai educate people about social issues. However, “the act is tortured out of shape, the pious fakir these days makes ridiculous gestures, wears senseless costumes and makes people laugh by hook or by crook” (Pathak, 2004). Thus, the researcher will also discuss the setbacks of this art form and the scope of Bhavai in the 21st Century.

Introduction

Traditional Indian Dance is originated from *Natyashastra*, written by Bharata Muni. He used ‘Pathya’ (words) from the *Rig-Veda*, ‘Abhinaya’ (gestures) from the *Yajur-Veda*, ‘Geet’ (music) from the *Sam-*

Veda and Rasa (emotions) from the *Atharva-Veda* to form the “Natya-Veda” that means a body of knowledge about dancing. Bharatnatyam, Bhavai, Kathak, Manipuri, etc. are the forms of Traditional Indian Dance. Bhavai, also known as ‘Swang’ or ‘Vesha’, is a folk dance drama originated in Gujarat. The Northern Part of Gujarat, Unjha is considered the home of Bhavai. The performers move from village-to-village or town-to-town to perform. The professionals are called

‘Bhavaiyas’ who belong to *Tar galas*. Apart from *Tar galas*, Bhavai is also performed by *Nai*, *Darji*, *Kansara*, and *Nagar Brahmin*. They not only have preserved this dance drama art form but also have adopted Bhavai as their profession. Asaita Thakar created its origin, who wrote around Three Hundred and Sixty-Five acts. However, over the years, only sixty have survived.

The Folklore

Once upon a time in the fourteenth century, Ganga, the daughter of Hema Patel, Unjha Headman, was kidnapped by a Muslim subedar. Asaita Thakar was their family priest. He went to subedar to save her and claimed Ganga as his daughter. During those times, Brahmins did not dine with lower caste. Subedar asked Asaita Thakar to dine with her in order to prove upon which he dines with her and returned with her safely. Soon, on return, he was out casted. The other version of the same story is that Asaita Thakar married Ganga Patel to save her and thus after being excommunicated, he started performing plays to earn his living. Out of gratitude, Hema Patel offered him a plot and financial support for his plays, which mark the start of patronage of ‘Bhavaiyas’, the performers of Bhavai by villagers.

Elements of Bhavai

Bhavai: A Medieval Form of Ancient Indian Dramatic Art (Natya) as Prevalent in Gujarat, by Sudha Desai discusses the elements of Bhavai such as troupe, veshas, plots, music, costumes and makeup. ‘Troupe’ (Tolam) is usually a group of nine to twenty performers of Bhavai who performs place-to-place. The Nayaks, the heads of the troupes, entitles villages or towns to the troupes to perform. A troupe consists of ‘Nayak’ (the head), ‘Veshacharya’ (the male roles), ‘Kanchaliyo’ (the female roles), ‘Ranglo-Rangli’ (the voices of conscience throughout the play), ‘Kamgaro’ (the labourers) and the instrument players.

‘Veshas’, commonly referred to the costumes worn by the performers. Veshas means ‘to wear the character through costumes and actions’ (Desai, 1972). Veshas can be divided into three parts: mythological, historical and social. Lord Ganesh, Goddess Amba, Sri Krishna, Ram-Laxman, and so on

are the parts of mythological veshas. Viko Sisodia, Raga Degam, etc. are the examples of historical and Kabo, Main Brahmini are the examples of social veshas. (Desai, 1972).

The play usually begins with the plots of Lord Ganesh and Goddess Kali or Amba to pay the homage to them and seek blessings. Then, the long or short dramatic sequences are called veshas. The acts are set in the form of Songs, Sonnets, Doha, and Prose Passages. The dialogues of the plot are incorporated in Gujarati but also includes the dialects of Hindi, Marwari and Urdu. Music plays an important role as it keeps the environment lively and active. The artists of Bhavai not only perform dance-drama, but also compose the songs and write the plays. They also play the instruments during performance and design the costumes themselves. Bhungal, Pavo, Vanasali, Tabla, Nagar, Kansi Joda, Cymbals, Karatala, Ektaro and Harmonium are the key instruments used for performance. The acts generally begin and end with dance including Garba (a popular folk-dance in Gujarat).

Fig.01: Setting of Bhavai)

As Bhavai is a lock dance form and performed on streets, the make-up is consists of kumkum, kajal and khadi. As it is considered purely a male art form, the female characters are also played by men. Specific

costumes are assigned to specific characters such as the saree of Goddess Kali is always black and only kumkum is smeared on his forehead. (Desai, 1972).

Setting of Bhavai

Bhavai is usually performed in an open space or near a temple. The Shrine of Goddess Amba is depicted through an earthen pot called 'Mandvi'. The Nayak draws a circle of about a twenty-foot diameter, which is an acting area. The musicians sit on one side and the acting area surrounds and faces the audience side.

Conclusion

Bhavai portrays people from all classes of the society as the theme is not restricted to mythological. Bhavai was introduced when the caste system was prevalent. So, the performances were also based on criticising the system with a pinch of humour and wit. It continues to address more socially relevant issues like Swachh Bharat in its performances (*Bhavai in Gujarat 2019-20*). Today, Bhavai is performed on the social, historical and even political themes that makes it still relevant in the 21st Century.

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